

EFFECTIVE WAYS OF ENRICHING LEARNERS' VOCABULARY SKILL

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Abstract. One of the most crucial abilities for teaching and studying a foreign language is vocabulary. It serves as the cornerstone for the development of all other abilities, including speaking, writing, spelling, pronunciation, and reading and listening comprehension. The key to helping kids use English successfully is vocabulary. Students will constantly need to use words, whether they are reading a text or sending a letter to a friend, watching a movie or listening to their favorite song, or conversing with a native English speaker.

Key words: language acquisition, active vocabulary, techniques, mnemonics, flashcards, visual aids, real life examples.

Teaching vocabulary is crucial. It is essential because without vocabulary, learners cannot talk, write, or grasp the meaning of a phrase or what others say. Vocabulary is an important aspect of second language competency; one of the basic aims of language acquisition is to understand the meanings of words.

Vocabulary plays an important role in oral language development and early literacy [1,47]. Paris [3,184] identifies vocabulary as one of the unconstrained skills, meaning that it is a skill that we continue to develop over our life span. Konza [3, 150] notes the importance of explicit teaching of vocabulary to support students to become confident in a word's meaning and use in context so that it will become part of their own repertoire.

Acquiring vocabulary is an ongoing process that starts in early life and continues through education and beyond. It is a part of the development of language and literacy. According to Sinatra, Zygouris-Coe, and Dasinger

Knowledge of vocabulary meanings affects children's abilities to understand and use words appropriately during the language acts of listening, speaking, reading, and writing. Such knowledge influences the complexities and nuances of children's thinking, how they communicate in the oral and written languages, and how well they will understand printed texts [4,333]

Vocabulary mastery is one of the components of learning English. The students are able to grasp and apply the meaning of words. Students must learn and recall a large number of words. By acquiring a variety of vocabulary, learners are able to understand what they heard and read, as well as express and write what they want to. Teaching English as a foreign language is not synonymous with teaching English as a second language. Teaching English as a foreign language entails instructing students in the target language so that they can communicate effectively in English. However, the setting do not assist students in learning English. The students do not utilize English outside of class. They only use English during English class. As a result, the learners do not have many opportunities to practice English in their regular activities. Learning and teaching English as a foreign language necessitates immersion in real-world situations that allow students to use English spontaneously. Teachers should integrate the real world into the classroom by providing activities that allow pupils to practice English. The teacher should use

media to teach English based on real-life situations, allowing pupils to practice the language freely and intuitively.

The following are the most significant techniques to help students acquire vocabulary more efficiently in their target language. Encourage learners to include vocabulary study into their regular routines. This ensures that students have the vocabulary necessary to communicate successfully in all forms of their target language.

➤ Make the new vocabulary relevant.

As with most learning activities, engaging learners increases the likelihood that the material will be retained. The same is true for vocabulary: we recall what is most relevant to us, therefore creating vocabulary lists with random terms is unlikely to be very useful! Encourage learners to strive to build a meaningful connection with the terms they are learning. If they're learning about cooking tools, urge them to place sticky notes on cupboards and drawers as a reminder. We also recall locations, events, dates, and songs that hold an emotional significance for us. It makes sense to try to learn vocabulary through games, movies, and music. Not only is it a unique technique, but it may also be quite beneficial for pupils to connect / correlate words with songs or films that they enjoy. It's evident that students should look up unfamiliar words in a dictionary first!

➤ Memorable mnemonics

Mnemonics are an excellent technique to improve memory and relevance, and they may be a very effective aid in language learning in general, as well as vocabulary acquisition in particular. A mnemonic is a pattern, concept, or association that students may use to help them recall information, however they are typically made out of visuals or word connections. The finest mnemonics are ones that learners come up with on their own, so encourage them to be creative!

➤ Write, Look, Cover, Repeat (WLCR)

This is a traditional method for learning vocabulary. Take a pen and a sheet of paper, draw a vertical line down the center of the page, and fill one side with words from your original tongue. Then, in your target language, write the same term opposite. Learn and memorize both sets of words before tackling one side of the list and attempting to recall the answers. Swap sides and repeat until you're satisfied with your progress

➤ Use flashcards to teach vocabulary.

Again, a traditional strategy that extends WLCR by introducing randomization. This method works effectively with real cards or with an app that uses digital flashcards. Easy, quick, and straightforward: just make word and/or picture sets in the mother tongue and target language of your students. Mix them up and put yourself to the test, either alone or with a partner.

➤ Focus on complex meanings rather than simple dictionary definitions.

Too often, vocabulary training consists of children transcribing definitions from dictionaries. However, researchers have found a variety of instructional methodologies that outperform any learning that may result from copying definitions. One of these fundamental concepts requires students to engage with more elaborate or complicated definitions or explanations of word meanings. Encourage encyclopedia explanations above dictionary definitions. When a teacher teaches vocabulary, he or she should ask the students to offer many possible definitions for a term.

1. Dictionary definition
2. Find synonyms for the word

3. Antonyms (if there are any)
 4. Part of speech
 5. Classification (what semantic group does it belong to, like tools or ways of talking)
 6. Comparison (similar to____, but different because_____)
 7. provide real-life examples
 8. Graphic version (drawings, photos, representations)
 9. Acting it out
- Emphasize the relationships between words.

Numerous vocabulary programs teach words according to categories, including terms related to health and medicine or transportation. Some of these programs are proven to be beneficial based on research. Direct study on this particular component of instruction, however, indicates that word acquisition proceeds more slowly and does not clearly benefit from the additional effort required to master these collections of words in the long run.

- Make use of it

The final vocabulary-building tip is as easy as it sounds: always encourage your students to apply the words and phrases they have learnt in meaningful conversations with friends or partners. It's a well-established truth that expressing words out loud to someone else helps you remember them considerably better than repeating them to yourself. This should come as no surprise, as students may improve their fluency and verbal memory the more, they actively interact with others. The key to learning a language is practice, practice, practice!

In conclusion, the most crucial ability while learning or teaching a foreign language is vocabulary. All other abilities, including speaking, writing, listening, and reading, are acquired and reliant on vocabulary. This demonstrates the significance of picking up new vocabulary. Students are better able to comprehend what they read and what other people are saying when they know more than 90–95% of the vocabulary terms. Students struggle to comprehend people and communicate their thoughts when they don't have a strong enough command of language. In all subject areas, including language arts, social studies, math, and science, vocabulary instruction is crucial. By learning several words at the students' disposal of describing events or emotions, they can be that explicit when sharing ideas their ideas and opinions.

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